

MELTOCENE: TOWARDS A NEW KAIROLOGY

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ABSTRACT

This article defines and presents a new kairological era, the Meltocene. A time always in motion, born of global warming processes, inscribed at the intersection of art, theory, and political ecologies.

From *Liquid Modernity* (Bauman, 2000) to *Dysphoria Mundi* (Preciado, 2025), several authors have described contemporary instability as a process of liquefaction, overload, or planetary dysphoria. The Meltocene proposes a new kairós with a new interpretation, emphasizing the understanding of instability, melting, and viscosity as utopia, epistemology, and method of creation.

It's 2000, and Zygmunt Bauman publishes *Liquid Modernity*; he lays the foundations for a new society, from which he postulates a modernity that slips through our fingers like water. Perhaps Bauman omitted a step in his analysis: the process of melting: *como un helado derritiéndose, como un helado derritiéndose*—as Battles sang in 2011.

It's 2018 and, for the first time in more than half a century, the *Hungersteins* appear. Placed in the beds of several European rivers these stones warn us: *Wenn du mich siehst, dann weine* (“If you see me, then weep” [1]). Finally, vulnerability is allowed to surface.

It's 2025, and Paul B. Preciado publishes *Dysphoria Mundi*, where “the epistemic-political planetary condition is a generalized dysphoria [...] Dysphoria points to a problem of burden, a difficulty of resistance.” [2] Faced with this unbearable burden, what better approach than to fail to grasp it, from the perspective of the viscous? Melting down as a resistance.

This framework suggests the definition of a new kairology [3]: the Meltocene [4]. An uncertain temporality characterized by fragility, informality, fluidity, and unpredictability at both the material and methodological levels, and whose epistemic nature is one of vulnerability, compulsion, and/or fixation. Within the blurred boundaries of the term itself, it is important to emphasize that the imagination of and from the term originates from utopia, attempting to counteract the crisis of imagination within speculative research and contemporary cultural practice.

Although an ambiguous temporality, the transdisciplinary study of the Meltocene can refer to a kairological genealogy specific to the viscous, focused on the first 25 years of the 20th century, with some antecedents such as:

· The 19th century: the prehistory of the Meltocene, when the fascination with slime moulds begins. Biological taxonomy describes for the first time *Physarum polycephalum*, a mass known literally as "the viscous organism." At the same time as the categorization of the mentioned mycetozoa (1822), it was in these decades (1850 onwards) that the trend of glacial retreat began to be documented on a global scale.

· The year 1938 marks the first publication on the global melting of glaciers by someone outside the scientific community (Guy Stewart Callendar). It was also the year of the discovery of plastics (nylon, plexiglass, polystyrene, polyurethane) and of some possible corresponding artistic expressions, such as the ones by Dalí, Jan Arp, Henry Moore, and Giacometti, and their fascination with unstable matter and soft, melting forms, of a liquefied time.

It is truly the 1980s—coinciding with significant global warming—that provide the closest kairological genealogy to the Meltocene, with the first viscous artistic manifestations of the late 20th and early 21st centuries that we will call 'blobic': forms that represent the impossibility of maintaining form (Bauman, 2000), such as the work of Lynda Benglis or Franz West, the trend of 'blobarchitecture' (Lynn, 1999), or the work of Tony Oursler.

The Meltocene seeks to study new ontologies of matter, post-Anthropocene bodies, and their non-hierarchical and collective modes of intelligence and growth. Interwoven with these characteristics are the theoretical foundations of Deleuze and Guattari's new materialism (the attribution of a specific intelligence to inorganic matter) and Bruno Latour's ontology (his idea of animism in Western culture and, again, the agency of things and objects).

In short, this term identifies a new era, as a *kairós*, with its own characteristics, defining its terminology for the first time and marking its artistic and cultural practices genealogy within its theoretical framework. These are almost unstoppable practices that take advantage of their viscosity to grow and relate; ultimately, to be. An alchemy as an encounter of opposites beyond the modern formula of the binomial: a third state—*Zwischenland*^[5]—where things are defined as natural and artificial; organic and inert; human and non-human. Always viscous: a becoming. These visually and formally amorphous practices as the ruins of today where global warming is the creative agent of a splendid assumed reality.

[1] "If you see me, weep" James, L. (16TH August 2022). ['If you see me, cry': Drought reveals 'hunger stones' in River Elbe historically used to forecast famine](#), *The Independent* [Retrieved 18TH November 2025].

[2] From the original: "la condición planetária epistémico-política es una disforia generalizada [...] Dysphoria señala un problema de carga, una dificultad de resistencia". Preciado, P., *Dysphoria Mundi*, Anagrama, pp. 13-14 (own translation).

[3] "...one might understand kairós to refer to a passing instant when an opening appears which must be driven through with force if success is to be achieved", White, E., C., *Kaironomia: On the Will-to-Invent*, p. 13.

[4] Originally coined in Spanish: 'Derretiloceno', I do understand 'Meltocene' as the proper translation.

[5] Taken from Lou Andreas-Salomé and her *Im Zwischenland* (1902), it is a term that will be translated as 'the land in between'.